

Strength Dispersion of C / E Composite Structure

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ABSTRACT

Strength dispersion of C / E composite structure is an important parameter for structure reliability design and the application of C / E composite material on airframe structure. This paper describes strength dispersion from application and macroscopic view, and define the range of variable coefficient C_{VS} of strength parameter and upper bound of C_{VS} (i.e. C_{VO}). Structure reliability could be analysed by reliability analysis method for known coefficient of variation by assuming that C_{VO} is parent parameter.

Keywords: composite mechanics, strength dispersion, variable coefficient

1. Strength Dispersion of C / E Composite Material

Growing interest in C / E composite material makes structure designer note the importance of strength dispersion. From the mean strength viewpoint, weight of composite structure could be decreased by 25%~40%. For strength dispersion of composite material is greater than that of metal, there exists two problems. One is how many percentage structure weight could be decreased, the other is how about the structure reliability. In order to answer these two questions, strength dispersion is studied.

Here, strength dispersion is variable coefficient C_{VS} , it is expressed in the ratio of strength standard deviation σ_S to strength mean value μ_S , i.e. $C_{VS} = \sigma_S / \mu_S$. For many engineering problems, there are only a few samples in a sample group, this makes defined strength dispersion (or coefficient of variation) unreliable. So large number of test data are analysed with statistical method to get coefficient of variation C_{VS} . Only this kind of statistical result has higher confidence.

Strength dispersion of C / E composite structure is studied from macroscopic view. For strength checking, laminated plate could be considered as anisotropic plate predicted by

theory and measured by test. Strength is analysed with Tsai–Wu strength criterion while uniaxial reference performance is determined by experiment. The method is also used for buckling problems. The calculated result is consistent with actual result.

1.1 Strength Parameter and Distribution Function of Variable Coefficient

- a. Strength and modulus of carbon fiber bundle approximately fits normal distribution. ¹
- b. For unidirectional plate, 0° tension, 0° compression and shear between laminates satisfies normal distribution, and ± 45° shearing strength approximately fits normal distribution. ²
- c. For cylindrical shell which undergoes uniform external pressure or axial–external pressure, critical value satisfies normal distribution, ⁶ see Figure 1 and Figure 2.
- d. Distribution function of variable coefficient approximately fits normal distribution. ³

Figure 1. Distribution function of critical value of C / E cylindrical(shell) under axial–external pressure

Figure 2. Distribution function of critical value of C / E cylindrical shell under uniform lateral pressure

1.2 Statistics of Strength Variable Coefficient

Statistics of strength variable coefficient is classified into three parts, i.e. ① raw material — carbon fiber and resin. ② unidirectional plates. ③ structure and joint. Variable coefficient of unidirectional plate horizontal strength parameter approaches to that of matrix's.

1.2.1. raw material

Variable coefficient C_{VS} of carbon fiber and resin is shown in Table. 1.

1.2.2. unidirectional plate

For strength parameter of unidirectional plate, statistical result of variable coefficient is

shown in Table. 2. Obviously, variable coefficient C_V of horizontal strength parameter is greater than longitudinal strength parameter, and C_{VO} approaches to C_{VB} .

Table. 1 C_{VS} of Jilin Carbon / 648 Epoxy Strength Parameter^{<4>}

Parameter \ Object \ Data	Carbon Fiber			648 [#]		
	E MPa	σ_b MPa	δ %	E MPa	σ_b MPa	δ %
Mean Value \bar{X}	2.265×10^5	3.623×10^3	1.583	3.635×10^3	29.66	0.826
Variable Coefficient C_{VS}	0.059	0.086	0.087	0.050	0.203	0.205
Sample Number n	30	28	28	7	7	7

Table. 2 C_V of C / E , GRP Unidirectional Plate Strength and Modulus^{<5>}

Object	n	\bar{X}	S	C_{VO}	Bound of C_V	C_{VB}	C_{VA}
C_V of C / E longitudinal tension strength	20	0.085	0.022	0.128	0.085~0.128	0.127	0.158
C_V of C / E horizontal tension strength	19	0.162	0.056	0.278	0.162~0.278	0.271	0.349
C_V of C / E longitudinal tension modulus	14	0.042	0.015	0.072	0.042~0.072	0.074	0.096
C_V of C / E horizontal tension modulus	13	0.056	0.033	0.123	0.056~0.123	0.127	0.177
C_V of C / E longitudinal compression strength	19	0.073	0.026	0.124	0.073~0.124	0.125	0.161
C_V of C / E horizontal compression strength	17	0.096	0.056	0.202	0.096~0.202	0.208	0.287
C_V of C / E longitudinal compression modulus	14	0.052	0.012	0.076	0.052~0.076	0.077	0.095
C_V of C / E horizontal compression modulus	13	0.066	0.028	0.123	0.066~0.123	0.126	0.169
C_V of GRP bending modulus	10	0.056	0.025	0.108	0.056~0.108	0.115	0.156
C_V of GRP laminated shear strength	9	0.042	0.015	0.074	0.042~0.074	0.079	0.104

Denotes: C_{VO} – confidence $r=0.75$, probability $P=0.95$

C_{VB} – confidence $r=0.95$, probability $P=0.90$

C_{VA} – confidence $r=0.95$, probability $P=0.99$

Table. 3 provides statistical data of fracture toughness K_C for 4:1 glass cloth – polyester. From these data we could get following conclusion. ① For ply angle from 0 to 60, variable coefficient C_V of K_C approximately equals to each other. ② For ply angle being equal to 90, C_V is much greater, and dispersion is determined by matrix.

Table. 3 Fracture Toughness K_C of 4:1 glass cloth – polyester

Ply Angle	Mean Value \bar{X} MPa	Standard Deviation S MPaM ^{1/2}	Variable Coefficient C_V	Sample Number n
0°	14.25	0.574	0.040	3
± 30°	8.95	0.434	0.049	3
± 45°	5.58	0.105	0.019	3
± 60°	4.57	0.205	0.045	3
90°	3.33	0.375	0.112	3

Table. 4 Test Data of Uniform External pressure on C / E Composite Cylindrical Shell^{<6>}

specimen gang-up	L cm	R cm	h cm	V_f %	experiment value X_{oi} Mpa	calculate value MPa	experiment value calculate value X_i	statistical parameter
JR-1	32.0	11.5	1.69	47	0.617	0.531	116	Statistics of experiment value $n = 16$ $\bar{X} = 0.4855$ $S = 0.0667$ $C_V = 0.137$
JR-2			1.64	47	0.625	0.507	124	
JR-3			1.64	48	0.517	0.508	102	
JR-4			1.62	48	0.542	0.483	112	
JR-5			1.41	55	0.467	0.411	114	
JR-6			1.47	55	0.467	0.455	103	
JR-7			1.48	56	0.450	0.462	97	
JR-8			1.35	57	0.450	0.370	122	
JR-9			1.41	58	0.467	0.440	104	statistics of X_i $n = 16$ $\bar{X} = 105.06$ $S = 10.62$ $C_V = 0.101$
JR-10			1.38	58	0.433	0.426	102	
JR-11			1.36	59	0.408	0.411	99	
JR-12			1.35	60	0.408	0.402	101	
JR-13			1.43	65	0.467	0.504	93	
JR-14			1.42	65	0.500	0.496	101	
JR-15			1.38	70	0.417	0.500	83	
JR-16			1.40	70	0.533	0.518	108	

Table. 5 Crushing Test Data of Titanium Rivet Joining C / E – Al Specimen

connection form and dimension of specimen						
ply	$[0_2^\circ / \pm 45^\circ / 0_2^\circ / \pm 45^\circ / 0_2^\circ]$					
technique	V_f	$\sim 60\%$	force	1882~3204(N)		
Object gang-up	main geometric dimension (mm)					P_{max} (N)
	W	t	D	e_1	$\sim e_2$	
C / AITMΦ4 —29	29.80	2.147	4	12	15	4668
C / AITMΦ4 —30	30.20	2.110	4	12	15	4000
C / AITMΦ4 —31	30.20	2.114	4	12	15	4300
C / AITMΦ4 —33	30.20	2.053	4	12	15	4122
C / AITMΦ4 —35	30.01	2.034	4	12	15	4069
statistical parameter	$n = 5$ $\bar{X} = 4230$ $S = 270$ $C_V = 0.064$					

1.2.3. Structure and its joint

Table 4 and Table 5 provide several groups of test data of external pressure, axial pressure of cylindrical shell and joint strength.

A group of crushing strength data is given in F-94, reference 2. Ply of laminated plate is $[45/0/-45/0/90/0/45/0/-45/0]$, nominal thickness is 0.125mm, force condition is double-face shear, the number of specimen is 45, and variable coefficient is 0.073, i.e. $C_V = 0.073$.

2. PROPOSITION AND DISCUSSION

①. Characteristic of variable coefficient C_V of unidirectional plate strength parameter. Variable coefficient of horizontal strength parameter is greater than longitudinal strength parameter.

In the same condition, C_V is proximity for ply angle $\alpha < 60^\circ$.

②. C_{VO} approaches to C_{VB} .

③. Variable coefficient of unidirectional plate strength parameter could be used for multidirectional plate, i.e.

Strength variable coefficient C_V (strength) = 0.07~0.130

Modulus variable coefficient C_V (modulus) = 0.04~0.072

④. Variable coefficient of composite shell critical stress (or load) is smaller than that of metal shell, i.e.

$$C_V (\text{composite}) < C_V (\text{metal})$$

The inequality is reasonable for geometric defect of composite shell is less than that of metal shell. As the environment effect on composite is much greater, it is reasonable to consider C_V of composite and metal is proximity while test data is deficient. i.e. for stability of composite shell, C_V of metal shell in the same condition could be used.

⑤. Variable coefficient of C/E composite rivet crushing strength $C_V = 0.1 \sim 0.16$.

⑥. For high and low temperature condition, variable coefficient of strength parameter in atmospheric temperature could be used.

3. PROSPECTIVE WORK

①. Do more test in order to determine C_V .

②. How do miscellaneous environments effect on C_V ?

③. How joint is damaged? Determine its variable coefficient.

④. The rationality of variable coefficient of atmospheric temperature structure insteads that of high and low temperature structure.

⑤. Angle effects of variable coefficient of unidirectional laminated plate strength parameter C_V .

⑥. The effects of thickness of unidirectional or multidirectional plate on variable coefficient C_V .

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